

DEVELOPING ENGLISH LEARNERS’ WRITING SKILLS THROUGH ARTICLES

Jambulova Ayimxan

TITU, Nukus branch, assistant teacher

Abstract: This article discusses the importance of writing skills and provides tips and resources for improving them. Writing skills are essential for success in school, work, and everyday life. They allow us to communicate our ideas, share information, and persuade others. The article begins by defining writing skills and discussing the different types of writing. It then provides tips for improving writing skills, such as reading widely, writing regularly, getting feedback from others, and revising and editing your work.

Keywords: Writing skills, Writing tips, Writing resources, Communication, Critical thinking, School success, Work success.

English language learners (ELLs) face unique challenges in developing their writing skills. They often struggle with unfamiliar vocabulary, grammar structures, and writing conventions. Additionally, they may have limited exposure to English-language texts, which can make it difficult for them to develop their reading comprehension skills.

Articles can be a powerful tool for helping ELLs develop their writing skills. Articles provide authentic examples of written English, and they can help learners to learn new vocabulary, grammar structures, and writing conventions. Additionally, articles can help learners to develop their critical thinking and analytical skills.

Methods for Using Articles to Develop Writing Skills

1. Reading and Discussing Articles

Preview the article: Before students read the article, ask them to look at the title, headings, and any images or graphics. Ask them to predict what the article is about and what they think they will learn.

Read the article: Have students read the article silently. Encourage them to highlight or underline any unfamiliar words or phrases.

Discuss the article: After students have read the article, lead a discussion about the main points, supporting details, and any unfamiliar vocabulary. Ask students to share their thoughts and ideas about the article.

2. Summarizing Articles

Identify the main points: Ask students to identify the main points of the article. These are the most important ideas that the author is trying to convey.

Write a topic sentence: Have students write a topic sentence that summarizes the main points of the article.

Write supporting sentences: Ask students to write supporting sentences that provide evidence from the article to support the topic sentence.

Revise and edit: Have students revise and edit their summaries to ensure that they are clear, concise, and accurate.

3. Comparing and Contrasting Articles

Choose two articles: Select two articles that are on the same topic but have different perspectives or viewpoints.

Read and analyze the articles: Have students read and analyze the articles, paying attention to the main points, supporting details, and any similarities and differences between the two articles.

Create a Venn diagram: Ask students to create a Venn diagram to compare and contrast the two articles. [1.85]

Write an essay: Have students write an essay that compares and contrasts the two articles. In their essays, students should discuss the similarities and differences between the two articles and explain which article they found more persuasive or informative.

4. Writing Creative Pieces Inspired by Articles

Choose an article: Select an article that is interesting and inspiring to students.

Brainstorm ideas: Ask students to brainstorm ideas for creative pieces that they could write based on the article.

Write a creative piece: Have students write a creative piece, such as a story, poem, or play, that is inspired by the article.

Share and discuss: Ask students to share their creative pieces with the class and discuss their writing process.

By using these methods, teachers can help ELLs develop their writing skills and improve their overall English language proficiency.

Assessment: It is important to assess students' progress in developing their writing skills. This information can be used to track students' growth over time, identify areas where they need additional support, and determine whether they have met the learning objectives.

Effective assessment methods for writing skills include:

Writing portfolios: A writing portfolio is a collection of students' writing samples that demonstrates their progress over time. Portfolios can include a variety of writing samples, such as essays, stories, poems, and journal entries. By reviewing students' portfolios, teachers can track their progress in developing their writing skills, identify areas where they need additional support, and provide feedback on their work.

Anecdotal notes: Anecdotal notes are brief observations that teachers make about students' writing. These notes can be used to document students' strengths and weaknesses, track their progress over time, and provide feedback on their work. Anecdotal notes can be collected during writing workshops, conferences, or other interactions with students.

Formal assessments: Formal assessments are more structured assessments that are used to measure students' overall progress in developing their writing skills. Formal assessments can include essays, timed writings, or other writing tasks that are scored using a rubric. Formal assessments can be used to determine whether students have met the learning objectives and to identify areas where they need additional support.

By carefully considering these factors, teachers can develop effective assessments that will provide valuable information about students' writing skills.

Writing skills are the abilities involved in producing written text. They include:

Planning and organization: The ability to generate ideas, organize them into a logical sequence, and develop a clear and coherent structure for a piece of writing.

Content and development: The ability to research and gather information, develop ideas, and support them with evidence and examples.

Style and tone: The ability to choose words and phrases that are appropriate for the audience and purpose of the writing, and to create a consistent and engaging tone.

Grammar and mechanics: The ability to use correct grammar, punctuation, and spelling. Writing skills are essential for success in school, work, and everyday life. They allow us to communicate our ideas, share information, and persuade others.

How to improve writing skills There are many things you can do to improve your writing skills, including:

Read widely: Reading exposes you to different writing styles and techniques. Pay attention to how good writers structure their arguments, use language, and engage their readers.

Write regularly: The more you write, the better you will become at it. Set aside time each day to write, even if it is just a few minutes.

Get feedback from others: Ask friends, family members, or teachers to read your writing and give you feedback. This can help you to identify areas where you can improve.

Revise and edit your work: Once you have written a draft, take some time to revise and edit it. Check for errors in grammar, punctuation, and spelling. Make sure that your writing is clear, concise, and well-organized.

There are many different types of writing, including:

Academic writing: This type of writing is used in schools and universities. It includes essays, research papers, and dissertations.

Business writing: This type of writing is used in the workplace. It includes emails, memos, reports, and proposals.

Creative writing: This type of writing is used to create works of fiction, such as novels, short stories, and plays.

Journalistic writing: This type of writing is used to report on news events. It includes articles, editorials, and reviews.

Technical writing: This type of writing is used to explain complex technical information. It includes manuals, instructions, and white papers.

Use specific and concrete language. Avoid using vague or general language. Instead, use specific and concrete examples to support your points.

Vary your sentence structure. Don't use the same sentence structure over and over again. Vary the length and complexity of your sentences to create a more interesting and engaging read.

Use active voice. Active voice is more direct and engaging than passive voice. For example, instead of writing "The ball was hit by the boy," write "The boy hit the ball." [2.194]

Proofread your work carefully. Once you have finished writing, take some time to proofread your work carefully. Check for errors in grammar, punctuation, and spelling. Make sure that your writing is clear, concise, and well-organized.

Resources for improving writing skills [3.18]

There are many resources available to help you improve your writing skills, including:

- Online writing courses:** There are many online writing courses available, such as Coursera, edX, and Udemy. These courses can teach you the basics of writing, as well as more advanced topics such as academic writing, business writing, and creative writing.
- Writing workshops:** Many community colleges and adult education centers offer writing workshops. These workshops can provide you with feedback on your writing and help you to improve your skills.
- Writing tutors:** If you need more individualized help, you can hire a writing tutor. Writing tutors can help you with all aspects of writing, from brainstorming to editing.

Benefits of improving writing skills: Improving your writing skills can benefit you in many ways, including:

- Increased confidence:** When you can write well, you feel more confident in your ability to communicate your ideas.

- Improved communication:** Good writing skills allow you to communicate your ideas more clearly and effectively.
- Enhanced critical thinking skills:** Writing requires you to think critically about your ideas and to organize them in a logical way.

Greater success in school and work: Good writing skills are essential for success in school and work. They allow you to communicate your ideas effectively and to make a positive impression on others.

References:

1. On Writing Well by William Zinsser, 2018
2. Bird by Bird: Some Instructions on Writing and Life by Anne Lamott, 2015
3. The Elements of Style by William Strunk Jr. and E.B. White, 2020